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Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers: Basis for A Proposed Health Education Program

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Chapter 1 Introduction

Background of the Study

As the COVID-19 pandemic continues, and transitions to an endemic stage, booster vaccines play an important role in personal, and public health. Convincing people to take boosters continues to be a key problem. Despite the availability of clinically tested, and effective COVID-19 booster vaccines, convincing people to accept boosters remains a significant challenge. As of 18 January 2023, only 15.3% of the total population in the United States (U.S.) had received the bivalent COVID-19 booster vaccine. In addition, previous research showed people in many countries, especially in low-income countries, are hesitant to receive COVID-19 boosters (Limbu and Huhmann, 2023).

In the early introduction of COVID-19 vaccines, vaccination hesitancy has been a serious problem to preventive measures. Booster dose vaccination acceptance, and vaccination behavior differ among people. As a result, understanding patients' perspectives on booster dosage vaccination is critical for both policymaking officials, and healthcare workers. Efforts are required to overcome hesitancy to take a booster dose. It is a challenge to comprehend the motivations, and problems influencing the acceptance of booster vaccination among Egyptian patients. Low acceptability of booster dose of COVID-19 vaccine among Egyptian patients were noted. Public health workers and policymakers must make sure that patients get clear information about COVID-19 booster dose (Tharwat et al. 2023).

Coronavirus disease 2019 has affected countries for few years, threatening public health, and disturbed normal social life. Vaccination is the most economical, and effective method for preventing, and controlling infectious diseases, including COVID-19. Vaccine hesitancy is a delay in acceptance or refusal of vaccines, in spite the availability of vaccines is a major challenge. Vaccine hesitancy varies with time, region, and the type of vaccine caused by factors like complacency, convenience, and confidence. Some people are eager to

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receive all vaccines, and some reject all vaccines, people with vaccine hesitancy lie within the continuum. The group of vaccine-hesitant persons includes those who refuse certain vaccines while accepting others, delay their vaccinations, or accept vaccinations but still have concerns (Huang et al.2023).

Deng et al. (2023) studied on parental hesitancy on COVID-19 booster dose noted that 64.1% were hesitant to vaccinate their children against COVID-19. Mothers were hesitate to vaccinate their children. Results showed that parents were hesitant to vaccinate themselves and those who got lower on their perception of their children's vaccination were more hesitant to vaccinate their children with COVID-19 booster dose. Vaccine hesitancy is not conducive to the global control of the current COVID-19 pandemic, and the existence will have adverse effects on people's physical, mental health, and social economy. Parents were hesitant to vaccinate their children against COVID-19 booster dose. Parents who were hesitant to receive the COVID-19 vaccine, and with negative views of the vaccine for their children were more hesitant to vaccinate their children.

Parinyarux et al (2022) studied on the hesitancy of parents on the COVID-19 booster dose. Fifty-eight percent of the respondents had vaccine hesitancy. Parents who refused COVID-19 vaccination for themselves or refused to vaccinate their children against any other diseases had statistically significant higher levels. The parents who had finished the COVID-19 vaccine had lower levels with statistical significance. Attitude towards COVID-19 vaccine, and perceived behavioral control of the parents negatively influenced with statistical significance.

Paudel et al. (2023) studied on the knowledge, and attitude toward COVID-19 booster dose. 68.0%, and 78.6%, had good knowledge, and favorable attitude toward COVID-19 booster dose. Females who had received a single dose of COVID-19 vaccine had significantly lower odds of having good onformation of COVID-19 booster dose. Participants with low educational levels, and received a single dose of COVID-19 vaccination, had an unfavorable attitude toward COVID-19 booster dose. It showed a satisfactory level of knowledge, and attitude toward COVID-19 booster dose in Nepal. Their positive attitude toward COVID-19 booster dose vaccine is a key to the patient and community safety. Health education, and communication will aid in improving the awareness and attitudes toward COVID-19 booster dose in such populations.

Low et al. (2022) studied on the hesitancy of mothers toward booster dose. About (27.2%) considered themselves vaccine hesitant. Fathers were more vaccine hesitant than mothers. Vaccine hesitancy was associated with a low household income, unvaccinated parents, knowing someone with an adverse reaction to the COVID-19 vaccine, and having a low level of trust in their child's doctor. Parental trust in their child's doctor was the most significant factor in determining vaccine hesitancy among parents. It concluded that newspapers and print media were the primary sources used in obtaining knowledge on COVID-19 vaccine safety and efficacy, especially among parents with high household income.

Huriuchi et al. (2021) made a study on parent's hesitancy on COVID-19 booster dose. People with lower satisfaction to social relationships were more hesitant to vaccinate their

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child among mothers in contrast to fathers who showed constant intention to vaccinate their child. It suggested that dissemination of targeted information about COVID-19 vaccine by means of communication, gender and people who are isolated during measures of social distancing may help to increase parental vaccine acceptance.

Taybe et al. (2022) determined the mothers' impression, and beliefs of COVID-19 booster dose vaccine during pregnancy and lactation. Only 22.9% of the participants were willing to participate in clinical trials of the booster dose of COVID-19 vaccine. The biggest motivator for participation was their desire to find the best vaccine during pregnancy/lactation, while the main barrier was exposing themselves, and their babies to more side effects. The study noted reasonable acceptance of vaccination in a sample of pregnant/lactating women. Vaccination hesitancy for the booster dose was in-line with similar studies on the primary series.

Migrino et al. (2019) surveyed the factors affecting vaccine hesitancy among families with children 2 years old and younger in two urban communities in Manila, Philippines. Most respondents believed that vaccines are protective, however, vaccine hesitancy rates among the respondents reached 36.4%. Respondents who believed in the protective nature of vaccines were less likely reported vaccine hesitancy, and refuse vaccination for their children due to negative media exposure. The main negative media information identified was related to the dengue vaccine, Dengvaxia. The events involving the Dengvaxia controversy contributed to a decrease in vaccine confidence. The role of mass media in vaccine hesitancy was highlighted, supporting previous evidence that vaccine-hesitant parents were more susceptible to media reports. The lack of association between the sociodemographic factors, and vaccine hesitancy implies that the determinants of vaccine hesitancy varied depending on context and setting.

Mataria et al. (2023) in their study on parents' hesitancy on COVID-19 booster that the proportion of parents in accepting to vaccinate their children against COVID-19 is 49%. The major reason for their acceptance is their belief that COVID-19 vaccine is necessary to fight against the pandemic, and the most common factor for parents' hesitancy to vaccinate their children against COVID-19 is their concern on vaccine efficacy, safety, and possible side effects. **They concluded that** the proportion of parents in accepting to vaccinate their children against COVID-19 is lower than the global level. To increase parental acceptance, authorities must focus on increasing their trust in the government, and in vaccine manufacturers.

Elkhadry et al. (2022) conducted their study on parents' hesitancy on COVID-19 vaccination. Relevant characteristics for hesitancy included, being the mother of the child, younger than 40 years, illiterate, unemployed, without health insurance, unvaccinated against COVID-19, refused to complete vaccinations, and not having chronic disease. It concluded that socioeconomic factors significantly affect parents' attitudes toward their child's vaccination. Increasing parents' awareness of the importance of childhood vaccination, especially among the risky group, may enhance their decision-making ability on vaccinating their children.

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Khatwari et al. 2023 determined the reasons associated with vaccination hesitancy among parents, the prevalence, and the characteristics of the parents who were hesitant to allow their children aged between 5 to 11 years old to be given the COVID-19 vaccines. Personal and social factors, affected their willingness to vaccinate their children with the COVID-19 vaccines. The age of the parents have a significant impact on their decision to vaccinate their children. Those between the age of 40–49 years of age were the most willing to vaccinate, compared to those 50 years or older who were resistant to vaccination. Female participants were more resistant to vaccinating their children, compared to their male counterparts. Saudis were more resistant to vaccinating their children compared to the non-Saudi participants. It concluded several factors that affect the parental willingness to vaccinate their children. These factors must be addressed when developing public health strategies to promote the COVID-19 vaccination of children.

Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework

The study used the Dorothy Johnson's Behavioral Systems theory. She defined Nursing as “an external regulatory force which acts to preserve the organization and integration of the patient's behaviors at an optimum level under those conditions in which the behavior constitutes a threat to the physical or social health, or in which illness is found. Behavioral theory helps unify, codify knowledge, and can guide the search for why people adopt, do not adopt, or abandon healthy lifestyles. Behavioral theory helps organize information into patterns that can be used to predict and therefore to prevent disease and injury.

The Change Theory of Nursing by Kurt Lewin is also adapted. He theorized a three-stage model of change known as unfreezing-change-refreeze model that requires prior learning to be rejected and replaced. In the study, the parents must change their behavior to accept that the booster vaccination is beneficial to their children.

Both theories are adapted in the sense that behaviors of mothers on vaccine hesitancy be transformed so as to understand the importance of submitting for booster dose vaccination. Their behavior would be changed for the betterment of their children. The study focused on the hesitancy of mothers on submitting their children for COVID-19 booster dose vaccination. It determined the respondents' profile, and the factors that contribute to the hesitancy of mothers along knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes.

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Chapter 2 Methodology

This chapter presents the research methodology which includes the discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive method of research with the questionnaire as data gathering tool to determine the factors that contribute to the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster. According to Best (2005); descriptive research is the process that goes beyond mere gathering and tabulation of data. It involves an element of interpretation of the meaning and the significance of what is described. Thus description is often combined with comparison and contrast involving the measurements, classifications, interpretation and evaluation.

Population and Locale of the Study

The respondents of the study were the 100 mothers of children who had been vaccinated with COVID-19 but hesitant to submit their children to booster dose. To represent the population, purposive sampling was used and was delimited to the mothers of the children with hesitancy to submit for booster dose. The locale of the study was in different barangays of San Fernando, La Union. They were the mothers who registered in the hospitals' logbook but were hesitant to submit their children for booster dose at the Vaccination Center in a public tertiary hospital in San Fernando, La Union where the researcher is in charge of vaccination.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized survey questionnaire based on previous studies and articles related to the study. Part I focused on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, number of vaccinated, religion, and place of residence Part II tackled the factors that contribute to the hesitancy of mothers in submitting their children for COVID-19 booster dose along knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes and socio-ethical.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the actual gathering of data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission is granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher requested and coordinated with the Chief of Hospital for the permission of conducting the study in the vaccination area of the hospital and in different barangays of San Fernando, La Union. After securing the permission, the researcher secured consent from the respondents. Gathering of data was done personally by the researcher during the scheduled time and date of vaccination.

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Chapter 3

Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the results based on the data gathered, its results and discussions.

Respondents' Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of children, monthly family income, religion and place of residence.

Age. The majority of the respondents were in the age bracket of 41-50 with a frequency of 44 or 44 percent, followed by those 31-40 years old with a frequency of 43 or 43 percent, and 21-30 years old with a frequency of 13 or 13 percent. It revealed that the mothers were adults.

Civil status. It can be gleaned that the respondents were mostly married with a frequency of 70 or 70 percent, followed by single with a frequency of 24 or 24 percent, those widow and separated with a frequency of 3 or 3 percent. It showed that the mothers were into marital relationship.

Highest educational attainment. The majority of the respondents were bachelors' degree holder with a frequency of 62 or 60 percent, followed by high school graduate with a frequency of 20 or 20 percent, with masteral units with a frequency of 10 or 10 percent, and elementary graduate with a frequency of 8 or 8 percent. It showed that most mothers finished their tertiary level of education as compared to other mothers.

Number of children. As gleaned from the table, most mothers have 1-2 children with a frequency of 52 or 52 percent, followed by those with 3-4 children with a frequency of 41 or 41 percent, and those with 5 and above with a frequency of 7 or 7 percent. It revealed that most mothers have an average number of children as compared to other mothers.

Monthly family income. The majority of the mothers had a monthly family income of P30,001 and above with a frequency of 36 or 36 percent, 10,000 and below with a frequency of 32 or 32 percent, P10,001-P20,999 with a frequency of 22 or 22 percent and P20,001-P30,000 with a frequency of 10 or 10 percent. It revealed that most mothers earn an average income for their families.

Religion. It showed from the table that majority of the mothers belong to the most dominated religion the roman Catholic with a frequency of 61 or 61 percent, followed by Iglesia ni Cristo with a frequency of 13 or 13 percent, Born again with a frequency of 12 or 12 percent, Jehovas' witness and Adventist with a frequency of 4 or 4 percent, and Protestants and Mormons with a frequency of 3 or 3 percent.

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Place of residence. It revealed that the majority of the respondents were residing in the rural areas with a frequency of 76 or 76 percent, and those in the urban area with a frequency of 24 or 24 percent. It is clear that most respondents came from the different barangays of San Fernando, La Union.

Factors that Contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers along Knowledge

Table 2 presents the factors that contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along knowledge.

The highest indicators are items numbers 1, 7, and 10 “contraindicated in children with allergy and anaphylaxis to foods and drugs,” “more on the prevention effect of COVID-19,” and “Given for 2 doses,” with a weighted mean of 4.00, 4.09, and 4.14 or “Agree.” It clearly showed that the mothers were aware that the vaccine is not given to their children when they have hypersensitivity to the vaccine and given in two doses, however they are hesitant to complete the required booster dose.

The lowest indicators are items 3, and 9, “not given to children with history of COVID-19 infection,” “given to decrease the incidence of pneumonia in children due to their immature and not fully developed immune system,” With a weighted mean of 3.42 and 3.59 or moderately agree and agree. It revealed that the mothers were aware on who will have the vaccine and its effects to children.

Overall on the Factors that contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along knowledge got an average weighted mean of 3.84 or “Agree.” It revealed that the mothers have the knowledge on the vaccine but were hesitant to submit their child for booster dose.

Factors that Contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers along Beliefs

Table 3 presents the factors that contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along beliefs.

The highest indicators are items numbers 2, 4, and 7, “Posts vaccination adverse reactions,” “Gives me the doubt of its safety to my child,” and “Causes me fear of its effects and long term impact,” with a weighted mean of 3.98, 3.86, and 3.83, or “Agree.” It goes to show that the mothers believed that the booster dose will create a more severe reaction to their children which might have longer effects on their child.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 6, 8,9, and 10, “I doubt in the COVID-19 booster efficiency,” “Is perceived not to benefit my child,” “Due to my negative views on the vaccine for my children,” and “Distrust in the vaccine efficacy and effectiveness,” with a weighted mean of 3.41, 3.24, 3.44, and 3.27 or “Moderately Agree.” It revealed that mothers aside from their hesitancy to submit their child for booster dose have the doubts that the vaccine really is effective to their child.

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Overall on the factors that contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along beliefs got an average weighted mean of 3.63 or “Agree.” It revealed that the mothers have their own beliefs on the benefits of COVID- 19 booster dose.

Factors that Contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers along Attitudes

Table 4 presents the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along attitudes.

It can be gleaned from the table that the highest indicators are items number 4, and 7, “I read more information on booster dose vaccination to clearly understand it,” and “Booster dose is recommended even those with comorbidities,” with a weighted mean of 3.86, and 3.51 or “Agree.” It revealed that the mothers find time to know more about booster dose and they believe that it is also given to those with other illnesses.

The lowest indicators are item numbers 2, and 10, “I will submit my children for booster dose without any hesitancy,” and “I will submit my child for booster dose in the health center,” with a weighted mean of 2.89, and 2.97 or “Moderately Agree.” It reflects that the mothers had really the hesitancy to submit their children for booster dose.

Overall, the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along attitudes got an average weighted mean of 3.34 or “Moderately Agree.” It reflects that the mothers had manifested the attitudes that lead to their hesitancy in submitting their children for booster dose.

Factors that Contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers along Socio-Ethical

Table 5 presents the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along socio-ethical.

It can be gleaned from the table that the highest indicators are items numbers 7, 8, and 9, “I decide, act and ethically validated before proceeding to submit my child for booster dose,” and “I incorporate into daily actions and decisions, particularly ones that will have a beneficial effect on my child,” and “I have the responsibility to act in a manner that is beneficial to my child, our family and the society,” with a weighted mean of 3.68, 3.78, and 3.90 or “Agree.” It reflects that the mothers carefully decide whatever actions they did for their children and family.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 1, and 6, “I control my emotions and build connections to others by participating in mothers classes,” and “The actions or decisions I make causes no harm to my child and the health facility, with a weighted mean of 3.39, and 3.44 or “Moderately Agree.” It revealed that the mothers cooperated with the activities of the health center however, they decide their actions based on their beliefs on the efficacy of the vaccine.

Overall, the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers along socio-ethical got an average weighted mean of 3.62 or “Agree.” It

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reflects that the mothers believe in all the mentioned indicators, however they showed some hesitations in submitting their children for booster dose.

Factors that Contribute to the Pediatric COVID-19 Booster Hesitancy Among Mothers

Table 6 presents the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers.

It can be gleaned from the table on the knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, and socio-ethical the highest indicator is along the knowledge aspect with a weighted mean of 3.84 or “Agree,” followed by beliefs with a weighted mean of 3.63 or “Agree,” socio-ethical aspect with a weighted mean of 3.62, or “Agree,” It goes to show that the mothers were aware on the benefits of booster but have the hesitancy in submitting their children for booster dose.

The lowest among the four indicators is on attitudes with a weighted mean of 3.34 or “Moderately Agree.” It revealed that the mothers have the attitude that they still have their doubts in submitting their children for booster dose. It might be related to their limited knowledge on the facts about the benefits of booster dose.

Overall, the factors that contribute to the pediatric COVID-19 booster hesitancy among mothers got an average weighted mean of 3.61 or “Agree.” It reflects that the mothers were aware on the COVID-19 booster but have the hesitancy in submitting their children to vaccination.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Age

Table 7 presents the results of the test of difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across age. Significant values are generated under knowledge and socio-ethical aspects.

This means that age affects the hesitancy of mothers toward vaccination of their children along knowledge and socio-ethical concerns. On the other hand, the mothers regardless of their age brackets share the same sentiments as to their hesitancy toward vaccination of their children with COVID_19 booster does along beliefs and attitudes.

Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Age

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Table 8 confirms through the Scheffe Test that significant differences exist across age along the knowledge aspect.

Significant positive mean differences are evident between 21-30 and 31-40, and 21-30 and 41-50 age groups. This indicates that the first groups have higher means as compared to the second groups. Furthermore, mothers who belong to the younger age bracket have shown higher mean values along knowledge as compared to the older ones. It revealed that younger mothers were more knowledgeable on COVID-19 vaccine than the older mothers.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Civil Status

Table 9 displays the results of the analysis of variances in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across civil status.

Computed F-values reveal significant results, indicating that the mothers differ in their knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, and socio-ethical considerations as to their hesitancy toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster shots. It clearly showed that mothers have varying views on their hesitancy of the COVID-19 booster.

Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Civil Status

Table 10 reveals the groups which have shown significant differences across civil status specifically on the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose. Scheffe Test results confirms that significant differences exist along knowledge, beliefs, attitudes and socio-ethical.

As to knowledge and attitudes, the positive mean difference indicate that single mothers have higher mean values compared to the married ones. The reverse trend is shown under beliefs. The negative mean difference proves that married mothers have agreed more on the provided indicators as compared to the single mothers. Considering the socio-ethical concerns, single mothers and widows have higher regards to it than the married moms.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Highest Educational Attainment

Table 11 presents the difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across highest educational attainment.

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Significant results are shown along knowledge, attitudes and socio-ethical. The mothers, on the other hand, have the same beliefs toward COVID-19 booster dose for children.

Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Highest Educational Attainment

Table 12 validates the existence of significant differences in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children along knowledge, attitudes and socio-ethical across highest educational attainment.

All the computed mean differences are negative values indicating that the second group in the compared groups have higher mean values than the first groups.

This further means that the mothers who have finished higher level of education have higher regards also to knowledge, attitudes and socio-ethical concerns toward COVID-19 booster dose.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Number of Children

Table 13 shows the difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across number of children.

The computed F-values along knowledge, attitudes and socio-ethical suggest significant results. This means that mothers show varied hesitancy toward the COVID-19 booster shot for children along these aspects. Meanwhile, the mothers share the same beliefs toward the booster dose when they are grouped according to the number of children.

Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Number of Children

Table 14 discloses that only the areas along knowledge and attitudes have shown significant differences.

The positive mean differences indicate that the first set in the compared groups have significantly higher mean values than the second sets. This means that mothers with less number of children have claimed more knowledge and agree more on the given indicators than the mothers with more children.

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ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Monthly Family Income

Table 15 presents the difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across monthly family income.

The computed F-values along the four areas are all considered significant, hence, significant results. There exists significant difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the COVID-19 booster dose for children.

Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Monthly Family Income

The results of the Scheffe Test on Table 16 verifies existence of significant differences along beliefs, attitudes and socio-ethical across monthly family income.

Along beliefs, the positive mean difference between the below Php10,000 earners and the above Php30,000 earners indicate that the mothers who belong to the lower income bracket have agreed on the given indicators more than those who earn more.

As to attitudes and socio-ethical, negative mean differences are shown. This means that the second set in the compared groups have provided higher ratings than the second sets. This means that the mothers who earn more have higher regard on attitude and socio-ethical concerns toward the COVID-19 booster dose for children when compared to the low earners.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Religion

Table 17 displays the difference in the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across religion. There exist no significant differences along knowledge and attitudes across religion.

This means that the mothers share the same level of knowledge and attitude towards the COVID-19 booster dose for children. Meanwhile, significant results are shown under beliefs and socio-ethical, hence, further test is needed to determine the specific groups which have shown significant differences. It clearly revealed that the mothers had varying beliefs or understanding about the vaccine because they have inadequate knowledge about COVID-19 booster.

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Scheffe Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Religion

The results of the Scheffe test which is displayed on Table 18 verifies significant differences that exist along beliefs.

The significant positive mean differences indicate that the first set in the compared groups have provided higher mean values as compared to the second set. This means that the mothers who are Roman Catholics, Iglesia Ni Cristo, Born again and Mormons have significantly higher level of agreement on the indicators under beliefs toward COVID-19 booster dose as compared to the mothers who belongs the Adventist denomination.

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose across Place of Residence

Table 19 shows the t-Test results on the difference in the hesitancy of the mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose across place of residence.

Significant results are shown along knowledge and beliefs with significant positive mean differences. This means that mothers who reside in the rural areas have higher knowledge and agree more on the beliefs toward COVID-19 booster dose for children. This might be due to the reason that they had more information about the booster doses since the healthcare workers are frequently going to the barangays for their home visits and barangay clinic consultations.

Relationship Between the Hesitancy of Mothers toward the Vaccination of their Children with COVID-19 Booster Dose and their Profile Variables

Table 20 reveals the relationship between the hesitancy of mothers toward the vaccination of their children with COVID-19 booster dose and their profile variables.

Positive significant relationship is revealed between knowledge and highest educational attainment. This means that the higher the level of education, the more knowledgeable the mother toward the COVID-19 booster dose for children. However, a negative relationship exists between knowledge and place of residence. This implies that mothers residing in the rural areas have higher knowledge compared to those from the urban areas.

As to beliefs, positive relationship exists with civil status. This means that mothers with significant others have higher regard the indicated beliefs toward the COVID-19 booster dose. Negative relationships exist with highest educational attainment, monthly family

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income and place of residence. This means that the lower the level of education, income and resides in rural areas, the more that the mothers agree with the beliefs towards the COVID-19 booster dose for children.

Positive relationships exist between attitudes and highest education attainment, monthly family income and place of residence. This means that the higher the educational attainment and income being earned by the mother while living in the urban areas, the more positive their attitude towards the COVID-19 booster dose for children.

Finally, socio-ethical aspect reveals a negative relationship with age and civil status. Hence, the younger and single the mother is, the higher their regard for socio-ethical concerns. On the other hand, positive relationships exist with monthly family income and religion. This implies that the higher the monthly income, the more they show concern for socio-ethical aspects.

Chapter 4

Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations formulated based on the findings of the study.

Based on the findings of the study, the following are concluded:

The respondent mothers were adults, into marital relationships, finished their tertiary level of education with an average number of children, earning higher income, belongs to the most dominated religion in the country, and most lived in the barangays of the city.

The mothers had adequate knowledge about the COVID-19 booster vaccination but somewhat in doubt that the pediatric booster dose is not given to children with the history of COVID-19 infection which led to their hesitancy

The mothers believed that there are adverse effects of the COVID-19 pediatric booster dose which made them decide not to submit their children for vaccination.

The respondent mothers expressed their attitudes to be more informed about the pediatric booster dose by reading more on COVID-19 booster vaccination to be clarified on their queries about it.

The mothers made sure they knew more about the pediatric booster before they finally decide their child for the booster dose vaccination of their child.

The mothers showed different levels of agreement on the indicators provided that affects their hesitancy in submitting their child for COVID-19 vaccination particularly along age, civil status, religion, and highest educational attainment.

Positive relationships exist in the different profile variables that lead to the hesitancy of the mothers in the booster dose vaccination of their children.

Based on the conclusions provided the following are hereby recommended:

The respondent mothers must be well-informed about the benefits of submitting their children for pediatric booster dose vaccination by regularly attending to seminars conducted by the health center or hospital.

The mothers must understand and learn that pediatric COVID-19 booster vaccination can be given even to those with comorbidities and previously infected with it.

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The respondent mothers must be enlightened on the possible adverse effects of the pediatric COVID-19 booster to be clarified which will convince them to submit their children for booster dose.

They must improve their attitude to accept that the booster dose is more beneficial for their children.

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